

Notes

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed-ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Picolinic Acid, Quinaldinic Acid and their *N*-Oxides with Ethylenediamine and Propylenediamine

D. PRAKASH*, S. S. PRASAD and O. P. GUPTA

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna-800 005

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In continuation of our earlier work¹, we extended our investigation to study some more novel mixed ligand complexes of alkali metals with a view to explore the mechanism of selective absorption of alkali metal ions by plants. The complexes of transition metals with ethylenediamine² and propylenediamine³ have been extensively studied earlier. However, a survey of the literature revealed that no report on mixed ligand complexes of alkali metals with ethylenediamine and propylenediamine.

The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of a number of complexes of alkali metals with ethylenediamine (en) and propylenediamine (pn).

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data of the complexes are listed in Table 1. All the compounds are fairly stable in dry air, but in moisture slight change in colour was observed which may be due to its

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour/ M p	Decom./ Trans temp. °C	Conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ mol^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	M
LiPicA.en	Dirty white	175d	4.3	49.50 (50.79)	7.05 6.34	21.28 22.22	3.50 3.70
NaPicA.en	Cream	250d	5.6	45.90 (46.82)	6.00 5.85	19.28 20.48	10.80 11.21
KPicA.en	Cream (shining)	280d	7.2	42.65 (43.43)	5.62 5.42	18.68 19.00	16.85 17.64
LiPicO.en	Dirty white	198t	5.0	46.80 (46.82)	5.88 5.85	20.25 20.48	3.40 3.41
NaPicO.en	Dirty white	214d	6.1	42.80 (43.43)	5.45 5.42	18.86 19.00	10.30 10.40
KPicO.en	Dirty white	230d	7.5	40.35 (40.50)	5.10 5.06	16.70 16.72	16.25 16.45
LiQuinA.en	Dirty white	280d	4.6	60.10 (60.25)	5.90 5.85	17.35 17.57	2.88 2.92
NaQuinA.en	White	290d	6.3	55.75 (56.47)	5.60 5.49	16.20 16.47	8.10 9.01
KQuinA.en	White	300d	7.8	52.95 (53.13)	5.25 5.16	15.15 15.49	14.05 14.39
LiQuinO.en	Pale yellow	195t	4.0	56.40 (56.47)	5.52 5.49	16.42 16.47	2.70 2.74
NaQuinO.en	Pale yellow	210d	5.9	52.82 (53.13)	5.20 5.16	14.10 15.49	8.10 8.48
KQuinO.en	Pale yellow	240t	7.3	48.20 (50.17)	5.12 4.87	13.95 14.63	13.00 13.58
LiPicA.pn	Dirty white	290t	3.9	52.80 (53.20)	7.05 6.89	20.50 20.68	3.40 3.44
NaPicA.pn	White	280d	4.5	49.05 (49.31)	6.50 6.39	17.98 19.17	10.28 10.50
KPicA.pn	Dirty white	260d	6.9	44.50 (45.96)	6.15 5.95	17.20 17.87	16.00 16.59
NaPicO.pn	Cream	270t	5.0	44.15 (45.95)	6.10 5.95	17.58 17.97	9.60 9.78
LiQuinA.pn	White	>300	3.5	61.50 (61.66)	6.28 6.32	16.48 16.60	2.55 2.76
NaQuinA.pn	White	290t	5.2	57.20 (57.99)	5.98 5.94	15.00 15.60	8.50 8.55
KQuinA.pn	White	250d	7.5	53.65 (54.73)	5.80 5.60	13.95 14.73	12.90 13.68
LiQuinO.pn	Cream	275d	3.0	56.20 (57.99)	6.10 5.94	15.25 15.61	2.50 2.60
NaQuinO.pn	Yellow	240t	5.2	52.85 (54.73)	5.70 5.61	13.98 14.73	7.25 8.07
KQuinO.pn	Yellow	225t	7.0	50.85 (51.82)	5.42 5.31	14.10 13.95	12.25 12.95

slow decomposition. Most of the complexes are soluble in polar solvents, but a few are sparingly soluble in non-polar solvents. The decomposition temperatures of these complexes are considerably higher than boiling point of the second ligand, indicating thereby their greater thermal stability.

Lower values of molar conductivity of the complexes in methanol (at 25°) indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

Infrared spectra of the mixed ligand complexes were recorded in KBr phase. The two NH stretching vibrations appear as broad or medium bands at 3400–3000 cm^{-1} . The shifting of these bands to lower frequency indicates coordination through N. The complexes show one or two bands in the region 1160–1000 cm^{-1} . The *cis*-complexes usually show four bands in that region⁴.

On comparing the vibrations of NH_2 in ethylenediamine/propylenediamine in their alkali metal salts complexes with that of the standards^{4,5} whose structures are already known, it is suggested that because of the similarity of the spectra, ethylenediamine/propylenediamine has a bridging *trans*-structure.

Further, to have more evidence regarding the *trans*-structure, the CH_2 rocking region (870–790 cm^{-1}) were also probed. In all the complexes two peaks appeared at 830–795 cm^{-1} , which indicate to *trans*-structure.

On the basis of above facts a bridging ethylenediamine/propylenediamine group with *trans*-configuration is proposed for these complexes.

Experimental

Picolinic and quinaldinic acids (AnalaR) were

used. The ligand picolinic acid-*N*-oxide⁶ and quinaldinic acid-*N*-oxide⁷ were prepared by the reported methods⁶.

Preparation of complexes: To a suspension of the alkali metal salt of picolinic acid/quinaldinic acid/picolinic acid-*N*-oxide and quinaldinic acid-*N*-oxide in absolute ethanol, ethylenediamine or propylenediamine was added in 1:1 mole ratio. The contents were refluxed for 0.5–2 h with constant stirring when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was cooled and the resulting solid was washed with absolute ethanol and dried at 100°.

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